

Which gene combination to test in wet lab? A pedagogical walkthrough of R code mechanics of ML based search engine for biologists/oncologists

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Abstract

Background: A machine learning based search engine design was recently published by Sinha (2024), which helps biologists/oncologists to locate gene combinations as (un)known biological hypotheses in the form of myriad of combinations of factors that might be affecting the pathway under certain conditions. This is done via ranking with the aim to cut short the wandering and cherry picking, in a vast combinatorial forest and facilitating them in choosing which combinations to test in wet lab. If proven true, these could lead to scientific discoveries and therapeutic interventions. **Results:** An adaptation of the published engine mined up a range of (un)explored combinations of genetic factors in the cell signaling pathways that were affected by ETC-1922159 (a PORCN-WNT inhibitor), after the colorectal cancer cells were treated with the drug. **Conclusions:** Here, a pedagogical walkthrough of the R code of machine learning based search engine is elucidated.

Keywords: Gene combination, Colorectal Cancer, ETC-1922159, Sensitivity analysis, Machine learning

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^{*}Which gene combination to test in wet lab? A pedagogical walkthrough

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1. Insight, innovation, and integration

Which gene combination to test in wet lab? This is a fundamental problem that biologists/oncologists face in their search for potential breakthroughs that could help understand the mechanism of cell biology leading to scientific discoveries and therapeutic interventions. To address this issue, an elucidation of an adaptation of a machine learning based search engine is provided. The manuscript explains the R code using an example of static data generated from colorectal cancer (CRC) cells that were treated with ETC-1922159.

2. Why use this code?

In my limited opinion, the following goals can be achieved using the published work -

1. Biologist/oncologist can download the available code in R (and with support from any personnel having R programming experience), and apply to their data sets to rank/prioritise unknown combinations of genes/proteins which might be working synergistically in a pathway.

2. Because of 1. biologist/oncologist will not have to struggle to search for combinations of interest. The rankings of the combinations shed light on how the combinations can be searched/located. Probably, this work will make life easier.
3. Based on these rankings, the modifications of the work will help in writing grant proposals for testing machine learning based discoveries. This will also help biologist/oncologist get financial support for their research.
4. Combinations of any order can be generated and ranked. However, computational resources might be required and the search engine might have to be fine tuned.
5. Finally, the work might help answer many questions in cell biology. Though experimental tests need to be conducted on the discoveries made by applying the above machine learning based pipeline.

3. Introduction

I developed a search engine to rank/prioritize unknown/unexplored combinations of genes that might be working synergistically in a signaling pathway Sinha (2024). Also, the foundation of this work is based on sensitivity indices. The use of these indices to study when and which genetic factor will have greater influence on the pathway has been published in Sinha (2017a). In order to understand the significance of the solution proposed to the problem of combinatorial search that the biologists face in revealing unknown biological search problem, these works are of importance.

This manuscript explains the sequence of the code in the pipeline that constitute the search engine. Note that the pipeline is generic in nature and can be modified, and here we present a possible solution to the combinatorial problem. This is to resolve the issue of finding potential combinations which might be working synergistically. These combinations are addressed as biological hypotheses. We will also address the issues in the paper as we move through the code and point out opening were the scientific community can work to refine the pipeline. Instead of considering these openings as loop holes, interested parties could tune/refine the pipeline as per their requirement. Currently, the code is broadly divided into three main parts that execute the following - • preprocessing and extraction of data • generation of sensitivity indices on measurements from the data and • ranking of the sensitivity indices. However, for a more professionalized version, the pipeline can be divided into smaller independent modules. The schematic diagram of the pipeline is represented in figure 1. Also, the code in R is presented and the coding is explained, where necessary. Note that explanation for the working of any particular package that has been used in the pipeline will not be provided. Instead, references will be provided for these packages or executable files.

4. Source of data

4.1. Description

Data used in this research work was released in a publication by Madan et al. (2016). The ETC-1922159 was released in Singapore in July 2015 under the flagship of the

Figure 1: Schematic view of the pipeline. Execution begins with preprocessing and extraction of data, followed by generation of sensitivity indices and culminating in ranking and sorting of the indices and the associated combinations. See steps 1., 2. and 3. Figure from Sinha (2024)

Agency for Science, Technology and Research (A*STAR) and Duke-National University of Singapore Graduate Medical School (Duke-NUS). Note that the ETC-1922159 data show numerical point measurements that is as Madan et al. (2016) quote - "List of differentially expressed genes identified at three days after the start of ETC-159 treatment of colorectal tumors. Log2 fold-changes between untreated (vehicle, VEH) and ETC-159 treated (ETC) tumors are reported." The numerical point measurements of differentially expressed genes were recorded using the following formulation of fold changes in equation 1 (see Tusher et al. (2001), Choe et al. (2005) and Witten and Tibshirani (2007)).

$$\log_2 \frac{VEH_{avg}}{ETC_{avg}} \quad (1)$$

4.2. Why choose this data?

The recordings of the gene regulations have been done by Madan et al. (2016) in the supplementary table 1. These recordings indicate (up and down) regulation of some 5000 genes which were made available, after the drug was tested on colorectal cancer (CRC) cells. Also, each recording is individual. But it is known to everyone in the field of biology/oncology that genes/proteins work in combinations. This work does nothing new or creative or modifies the data, however it reveals/ranks these gene combinations (whether tested experimentally or yet to be explored/tested) that might be working

synergistically, using an adaptation of published machine learning based search engine (see Sinha (2024)). Thus it solves an important problem of discovering which gene combinations to test wet lab, in a vast combinatorial search forest, via the use of a real life data. These point to efficacy and potential of the search engine. The engine is effective for ranking combinations of any gene of choice and any order of interest.

I tested the modification of the search engine in Sinha (2024) and discovered various 2nd order combinations of genes that might affect various pathways, after the drug was administered. **A few of the unpublished results of the work, using this R code, were shared as well as presented as a poster, in the first Wnt Gordon Research Conference titled - Wnt Signaling: A Pathway Implicated in Animal Development, Stem Cell Control and Cancer in 2017, from 6-11 August, held in Stowe, Vermont 05672, USA.**

5. Steps of execution via code elucidation

Fonts used for different constituents of the code - • variables in file and arguments in *italics*; • file names in sans serif; • functions in **bold**; • R code is in verbatim.

5.1. Preprocessing of ETC-1922159 data

We begin with the first step of the search engine by processing the data that has been provided in Madan et al. (2016). Note that the data had to be manually preprocessed in order to store it in a desired format in a file (here a .txt file). Since the file contained a list of both down and up regulated genes, it was necessary to segregate them in two files. A snap shot of the manually preprocessed file is shown in figure 2. In this file, the down regulated genes affected by ETC-1922159 have been stored. The orange boundary in figure 2 contains the file header with different columns separated by a delimiter, here, "+" symbol (see the magnification in blue). The columns include the titles • *GeneSymbol* or name of abbreviated name of gene, • *ENSEMBLgeneID* (not used in this code), • *GeneDescription* containing a short detail of gene, • *log2foldchange(VEH/ETC)* which represents the numerical point measurement and *BH-adjustedP-value* which represents the changes in gene expression were considered significant if the Benjamini-Hochberg adjusted P-value <0.0001 (not used in this code). An instance of the tuple in orange boundary is depicted by specific recorded values for instance tuple in red boundary. So, of particular interest would be gene MCM4 and its recorded fold change value of 3.03, from the red boundary, however, before we do that, we need to put the stored information in the .txt file in a particular format for further processing. After manual processing, we stored the list of down and up regulated files in the following two files onc2015280x2-A.txt and onc2015280x2-B.txt, respectively.

5.2. Extraction of ETC-1922159 data

Once the data has been stored in the required format after manual preprocessing, the next step involves the extraction of data from these files and storage of the information in a requisite format. This is done using the file extractETCdata.R which contains the

(A) Genes down-regulated after ETC-159 treatment

Genesymbol+ENSEMBLgeneID+Genedescription+log2foldchange(VEH/ETC)+BH-adjustedP-value									
RRM2+ENSG00000171848+rbonucleotide reductase	M2	[Source:HGNC Symbol;Acc:10452]	+4.93	+1.2E-162					
MKI67+ENSG00000148773+marker of proliferation Ki-67	[Source:HGNC Symbol;Acc:7107]	+4.35	+1.0E-142						
CLDN2+ENSG00000165376+claudin 2	[Source:HGNC Symbol;Acc:2041]	+5.03	+2.3E-130						
CENB1+ENSG00000134057+cyclin B1	[Source:HGNC Symbol;Acc:1579]	+3.99	+5.3E-129						
MCM4+ENSG00000104738+minichromosome maintenance complex component	4	[Source:HGNC Symbol;Acc:6947]	+3.03	+1.4E-128					
CDCA7+ENSG00000144354+cell division cycle associated	7	[Source:HGNC Symbol;Acc:14628]	+5.74	+9.6E-117					
FOXM1+ENSG00000111220+forkhead box M1	[Source:HGNC Symbol;Acc:3818]	+4.39	+1.8E-112						
UBE2C+ENSG00000175747+ubiquitin-conjugating enzyme E2C	[Source:HGNC Symbol;Acc:15937]	+3.99	+5.3E-106						
TOP2A+ENSG00000131740+topoisomerase (DNA) II alpha 170kDa	[Source:HGNC Symbol;Acc:11989]	+4.90	+1.0E-104						
MCM6+ENSG00000007660+chromosome maintenance complex component	6	[Source:HGNC Symbol;Acc:6949]	+4.19	+7.6E-100					
STMN1+ENSG00000117632+stathmin 1	[Source:HGNC Symbol;Acc:6510]	+4.22	+2.3E-96						
CDCA5+ENSG00000146670+cell division cycle associated	5	[Source:HGNC Symbol;Acc:14626]	+4.82	+4.5E-95					
PRC1+ENSG00000198901+protein regulator of cytokinesis	1	[Source:HGNC Symbol;Acc:9341]	+3.16	+4.0E-94					

Figure 2: A snapshot of the manually processed file. In this file, the down regulated genes affected by ETC-1922159 have been stored. Orange boundary - contains the file header with different columns separated by a delimiter, here, "+" symbol.

function `extractETCdata`. We begin with the explanation of the code in a sequential manner below.

5.2.1. Description of `extractETCdata.R`

The function `extractETCdata` takes in the argument with the name `data.type` that is a numerical value. Here, if the `data.type = 1(2)` then name of the file containing down(up) regulated genes is stored in the `filename`. The `if` condition is used for assigning the file name to `filename` with the condition as argument `data.type == 1` (See lines 1-7 below).

```

1 extractETCdata <- function(data.type){
2   if(data.type == 1){
3     filename <- "../data/onc2015280x2-A.txt"
4   }else{
5     filename <- "../data/onc2015280x2-B.txt"
6   }
7 }

```

Next, the total number of lines needs to be known once the file to be worked on has been decided. This is required in order to know the number of entries in the file, which gives the list of genes. The processing begins with the `system` command which executes Unix utilities like `wc` or word count with an option to count lines `l`. We use the option of `intern` to capture the output of the command `wc` in the output (see line 9 below). The output from the command is stored in `lineCnt`. This output is in the form of a string and the goal is to know the line count from this string. To proceed, the `strsplit` function is used in order to break up string in `lineCnt` into the atomic elements. Further, since

the output of the **strsplit** is in the form of a list, to simplify the data structure, **unlist** is used to produce a vector of atomic elements with an argument **strsplit(lineCnt, " ")**. So here the output of **strsplit(lineCnt, " ")** goes as argument in the function **unlist**. The output of **unlist** which is a vector is stored in *x* (see line 10 below). Next, to extract the numerical value of the number of lines in the file, a **for** command is run, where the iterator *i* takes in one element of vector in *x* at a time (see line 11 below) and tests if it is a numeric value. If a numeric value is found, the **for** loop breaks, else continues with the next element of *x* in the iterator. So, for every value of *x* in *i*, **if** value in *i* as numeric is not found to be true or is missing/not available, the iterator moves to the next element of *x*. Else, if the value in *i* as numeric is found to be true in the **if** condition, then this value is assigned to *nLines* and the execution breaks out of the **for** loop (see lines 11-14).

```

8 # find total number of lines in the file
9 lineCnt <- system(command=paste("wc -l ",
    filename,sep=""),intern=TRUE)
10 x <- unlist(strsplit(lineCnt," "))
11 for(i in x){
12   if(is.na(as.numeric(i))){}
13   else{nLines <- as.numeric(i); break;}
14 }
15

```

Once we know the number of lines in the file, we proceed to extract the information in the file, line by line. Lines 20-84 below contain the part of code that will extract the information from the file. However, due to the length of the code, the explanation is broken up into parts. The entire code for extracting the information is contained in the block within the **while** loop, which starts from line 20. The **while** runs till a condition is no longer true. Before that, the file needs to be opened for processing. This is done using the **file** command which takes in *filename* as the argument for variable *description* and *r* to read, as the argument for variable *open*. This opens the connection for the file of interest and the connection to the file is stored in a variable *connectTion*. We also set the variable *cnt* to 0 as an iterator for the **while** loop that needs to execute as long as the condition $cnt \leq nLines$ as argument to the **while** is met (see line 20). If the condition in line 20 is not met, the execution exits the **while** loop block.

Once inside the condition is satisfied, the counter is incremented by 1, stating that the first line is being read. This is indicated by updated *cnt* value in line 21. Next, the *cntth* line is read from the file using the function **readLines** which take in as arguments the value in *connectTion* and *n* (as 1 to read only one line). The output is the *cntth* line that is stored in *sentence*. For processing purpose the sentence is concatenated with a return character. However, if the *cntth* line is the first line, then the loop just skips it and jumps to the next line in the file (see lines 16-24).

```

16 # extraction information from the file
17 connectTion <- file(description = filename,
    open = "r")
18 cnt <- 0

```

```

19 #browser()
20 while(cnt <= nLines){
21   cnt <- cnt + 1
22   sentence <- readLines(con = connection,
                          n = 1)
23   cat(sentence, "\n")
24   if(cnt == 1){}

```

However, if the cnt^{th} line is the 2^{nd} one in the file, then we know that it contains the information on column names. This needs to be extracted from the *sentence* variable in the second iteration of the **while** loop which extends from lines 25 to 59. Again, to explain the aspects of the code, we will break this **else if**(*cnt* = 2){...} block into parts. This block contains two **for** loop blocks. The first block is used to retrieve the names of the columns that are delimited by a "+" sign (see lines 25-45). The second block is to create corresponding variable names that match with the retrieved names followed by initialization (see lines 46-58).

The **else if** block begins with a few initializations. The cnt^{th} sentence is split and stored in a simple format in *tempSentence*. The length of the sentence in terms of the number of characters is stored in *tempSentenceLength*. The position of the delimiter "+" within the sentence is also stored using the **which** function. Finally, the names of the columns need to be stored in *cnames* and an index *indx* is used as a start position at a particular location in *tempSentence* for processing purpose. In the first **for** loop, with the iterator *i* taking on values of the position of the delimiter (stored in *delimPlusPos*) one at a time in every loop, a particular piece of code is executed depending on the value of the index position in *indx*. In line 31, if the location of the *indx* is 1, i.e the starting character of the sentence, then the first name needs to be extracted that lies between position *I* and position (*i*-1). Note at location *i*, there is a "+" symbol. To execute this, the command **capture.output** is used that converts the concatenated elements of *tempSentence*[1:(*i*-1)] via **cat** command (see line 33). **capture.output** converts the input argument in a string and stores the retrieved name in *tempName*. Next, this column name is stored in *cnames* in line 34. In case the *indx* is the position which contains the last delimiter i.e. **length**(*delimPlusPos*) then the last and the penultimate column names need to be retrieved. The penultimate column name can be retrieved from the characters between the penultimate delimiter and the last delimiter, i.e *delimPlusPos*[*indx*-1]+1):(i-1) (see line 36). The last column name can be retrieved after the last delimiter and end of the sentence, i.e *delimPlusPos*[*indx*]+1):*tempSentenceLength* (see line 38). Finally, if the iterator neither points to the 1st or the last **length**(*delimPlusPos*) delimiter position, then the column name can be retrieved from characters lying between the position of the previous delimiter position and current delimiter position, i.e (*delimPlusPos*[*indx*-1]+1):(i-1) (see line 41). Each of these are ranges that are encased in the vector *tempSentence* and are concatenated via **cat** and captured in *tempName* and later stored in *cnames*. After the execution of the **for** loop ends, that is the iterator *i* has covered all the delimiter positions in *delimPlusPos*, *cnames* contains all the column names (see lines 31-45).

```

25   else if(cnt == 2){

```

```

26 tempSentence <- unlist(strsplit(
      x = sentence, split = "+"))
27 tempSentenceLength <- length(tempSentence)
28 delimPlusPos <- which(tempSentence == "+")
29 cnames <- c()
30 indx <- 1
31 for(i in delimPlusPos){
32   if(indx == 1){
33     tempName <- capture.output(
34       cat(tempSentence[1:(i-1)], sep=""))
35     cnames <- c(cnames, tempName)
36   }else if(indx == length(delimPlusPos)){
37     tempName <- capture.output(cat(
38       tempSentence[(delimPlusPos[indx-1]+1):
39         (i-1)], sep=""))
40     cnames <- c(cnames, tempName)
41     tempName <- capture.output(cat(
42       tempSentence[(delimPlusPos[indx]+1):
43         tempSentenceLength], sep=""))
44     cnames <- c(cnames, tempName)
45   }else{
46     tempName <- capture.output(cat(
47       tempSentence[(delimPlusPos[indx-1]+1):
48         (i-1)], sep=""))
49     cnames <- c(cnames, tempName)
50   }
51   indx <- indx + 1
52 }

```

Once the names of the column has been stored, the corresponding variables need to be created and initialized. This is done in the second block as described above. The second **for** loop iterates through the list of column names. In each iteration of the **for** loop, a condition is checked which tests whether a particular pattern exists within the column name under consideration. If the condition is satisfied, as above, the corresponding variable is created and initialized. We use the **grep** function to find the *pattern* in the column name *i*, as *i* iterates through *cnames* in the **for** loop. If there is a match and the *pattern* exists in column name *i*, then the length of this match will not be equal to 0, like `(length(grep(pattern = "sym", x = i)) != 0)` on line 47. When this happens, the creation and initialization of a variable follows. In the above example, *Genesymbol* is created and initialized. Finally, the block for **else if** is completed, if one is dealing with the 2nd line of the file (see lines 46-58).

```

46 for(i in cnames){
47   if(length(grep(pattern = "sym",
48     x = i)) != 0){
49     Genesymbol <- c()

```

```

49   }else if(length(grep(pattern = "ID",
50     x = i)) != 0){
51     ENSEMBLgeneID <- c()
52   }else if(length(grep(pattern = "des",
53     x = i)) != 0){
54     Genedescription <- c()
55   }else if(length(grep(pattern = "fold",
56     x = i)) != 0){
57     logTwoFC <- c()
58   }else if(length(grep(pattern = "value",
59     x = i)) != 0){
60     BAdjustedPvalue <- c()
61   }
62 }

```

Next, for all cnt^{th} line of the file that is neither 1st or 2nd, the last part of the **else** block for the **while** loop in line 20 is executed. This block is encoded in lines 59-82. Most of the code is similar to the preceding block with a few changes. Line 60 contains the same command to store the sentence read at cnt^{th} line of the file and line 61 is used to find the positions where the delimiter is positioned. In the next step, if there is an error in positioning of the delimiter due to manual preprocessing error, the command shows that correction needs to be done at line cnt . From lines 64 to 83, the coding is similar to the foregoing piece of code, except that if the index $indx$ is 1, now, the name of the gene is stored in *Genesymbol*; if the index $indx$ is **length**(*delimPlusPos*) then \log_2 fold change values are stored in *logTwoFC* from the left side of the delimiter and adjusted P-values are stored in *BAdjustedPvalue* from the right side of the delimiter; if $indx$ is 2, then ENSEMBLgeneID value is stored in *ENSEMBLgeneID* and finally, if $indx$ is 3, then Genedescription is stored in *Genedescription*. Lines starting with # are commented and used only for testing purpose and do not give any value (see lines 59-84). Note that as each line is read, information is stored using **rbind** function that keeps attaching or binding the current value to the existing vector in a variable. For example, *Genesymbol* <- **rbind**(*Genesymbol*, *tempName*) will append *Genesymbol* with the current *tempName* thus increasing the size of the vector in *Genesymbol* by 1. This procedure gets repeated. Thus ends the storage of information regarding from the file in the variables.

```

59   }else{
60     tempSentence <- unlist(strsplit(
61       x = sentence, split = "+"))
62     delimPlusPos <- which(tempSentence == "+")
63     if(length(delimPlusPos) != 4){
64       cat("Correction needed at - ",cnt);
65       break
66     }
67   }
68   indx <- 1
69   for(i in delimPlusPos){

```

```

65   if(indx == 1){
66     tempName <- capture.output(cat(
        tempSentence[1:(i-1)],sep="")
67     Genesymbol <- rbind(Genesymbol, tempName)
68   }else if(indx == length(delimPlusPos)){
69     tempName <- capture.output(cat(
        tempSentence[(delimPlusPos[indx-1]+1):
        (i-1)], sep="")
70     logTwoFC <- rbind(logTwoFC,
        as.numeric(tempName))
71   #   tempName <- capture.output(cat(
        #     tempSentence[(delimPlusPos[indx]+1):
        #     (tempSentenceLength-1)], sep="")
72     tempName <- capture.output(cat(
        tempSentence[delimPlusPos[indx]+(1:7)],
        sep="")
73     BAdjustedPvalue <-
        rbind(BAdjustedPvalue, tempName)
74   }else if(indx == 2){
75     tempName <- capture.output(cat(
        tempSentence[(delimPlusPos[indx-1]+1):
        (i-1)], sep="")
76     ENSEMBLgeneID <- rbind(ENSEMBLgeneID,
        tempName)
77   }else if(indx == 3){
78     tempName <- capture.output(cat(
        tempSentence[(delimPlusPos[indx-1]+1):
        (i-1)], sep="")
79     Genedescription <-
        rbind(Genedescription, tempName)
80   }
81   indx <- indx + 1
82 }
83 }
84 }

```

Next, we close the open file using the command **close** with an argument *connecTion*. And finally, we combine the variable names in a data frame, a kind of data structure using **data.frame** and arguments *Genesymbol*, *ENSEMBLgeneID*, *Genedescription*, *logTwoFC* and *BAdjustedPvalue*. The data frame is stored in the variable *oncETC*. Finally, the return command returns this data frame as output using the function **return** and *oncETC* (see lines 85-89).

```

85   close(connecTion)
86
87   oncETC <- data.frame(Genesymbol,

```

```

    ENSEMBLgeneID, Genedescription,
    logTwoFC, BHadjustedPvalue)
88 return(oncETC)
89 }

```

Note that the preprocessing and extraction of data can have different flavours depending on the type of data and experiment one is dealing. However, the output of the extraction should be a data frame (a kind of variable in R) containing the extracted data that needs to be used in sensitivity analysis. This is explained next.

5.2.2. Exercise

As an exercise, the readers are encouraged to build their own preprocessed file manually, from the data given in Madan et al. (2016) and see if they can reproduce the results in the form of a data frame using the function **extractETCdata**.

5.3. Computing the sensitivity indices

We move on to the next stage of the pipeline where the sensitivity indices need to be generated. Why we are generating these indices and how it helps in ranking up a set of factors and its combinations involved in the pathway have been discussed in Sinha (2017b) and Sinha (2017c). Here we concentrate on the implementation of the pipeline and explanation of the code only. The code has been saved in the file name manuscript-2-2.R and one of the author has been lazy enough not to change the name of the code. However, it also points to the fact that the author is not concerned with the show of expertise in nomenclature of file names and neither does he wish to earn a PhD in nomenclature of file names. Moving to the main topic, the code begins with the definitions of some functions and inclusion of packages from which specific function can be used during programming.

5.3.1. Description of manuscript-2-2.R

Here, the **library** function is used to call the package "sensitivity" which has been implemented in R and goes as an argument into the function **library**. Details of the package can be found in Pujol et al. (2016). Next we define a function, using the function **function** and give this function a name **new.name**. The function takes in as argument, a two dimensional matrix X . k is the number of genes under consideration out of a set of genes. The **new.name** implements the g-function (a model) that is used to assign weights to each of the genes, with a random weight. For this, **runif** function is used. b is updated as each gene is considered one at a time in the **for** loop. At the end of the function, value in **b** is returned implicitly. What happens is as the loop iterates **length(a)** times, where the expression shows the number of genes the user has selected. Note that length if a is computed using the value of k . This function read within lines 3-10. Also, **genSampleComb** is a function which returns a two dimensional matrix with the a specific number of columns defined in $yCol$. More about this function will be talked at a later stage. Here, definitions of the functions are provided (see lines 1-14).

```

1  library(sensitivity)
2  # Function definitions
3  new.fun <- function(X){
4    a <- runif(k)
5    b <- 1
6    for (j in 1:length(a)) {
7      b <- b * (abs(4 * X[, j] - 2) +
8        a[j])/(1 + a[j])
9    }
10 }
11
12 genSampleComb <- function(yCol){
13   return(disty[,yCol])
14 }
15

```

Since the code can be adapted for different data sets, a query is asked to the user regarding the generation of distribution around point measurements, if they exist in the data under consideration. To query the user, the function **readline** is employed. The user has to type in the option provided in the query for a particular functionality to take affect. Here, the response to the query is stored in the variable *DISTRIBUTION*. Next, if the response in *DISTRIBUTION* is a yes, that is, the user typed in "y", then the ensuing block within the **if** command will get executed, else it will be skipped. Again, the block under consideration, defines a new function **gdfetppv** which takes in arguments *n* and *yt*, were *n* contains the number of points which a user might want to generate for a distribution around a numerical point estimate. The measured numerical point estimates for each gene under consideration are assorted in a vector *yt*. The length of *yt* shows the number of genes involved in the study of sensitivity analysis. As the **for** iterates through each gene, for the corresponding numerical point estimate for a partipular gene, a distribution around the point estimate is generated with the mean value being *yt[i]* (*i* is the iterator) and a standard deviation of 0.005. Along with the distribution a minor jitter or noise is added. Thus, the whole distribution is stored in a vector. Note that the output of the **jitter** function is a vector and R stores vector in column format. Consequently, as the **for** loop iterates from one gene to another, the columns are bound together using a column binding function **cbind**. Thus, *randyt* keeps on increasing column wise, till all genes have been covered. Once out of the loop, the row vector *yt* is appended with the distribution matrix *randyt* using row binding function **rbind**. The output of the function is a two dimensional matrix containing the point estimate in the first row and the corresponding distribution in the rows below (see lines 20-28).

```

16 # Generation of distributions
17 DISTRIBUTION <- readline("Should i generate
18   distribution of data [y/n] - ")
19 if(DISTRIBUTION == "y"){

```

```

20  gdfetppv <- function(n,yt){
21    randyt <- c()
22    lenyt <- length(yt)
23    for(i in 1:lenyt){
24      randyt <- cbind(randyt,
25                      jitter(rnorm(n, mean = yt[i],
26                                sd = 0.005), factor = 1))
27    }
28  }
29 }

```

After the functions have been defined, the main execution begins. The code starts with the extraction of the data using the **readline** argument and provides an option to the user to choose a file that contains data regarding down regulated genes or up regulated genes. Once the response is recorded, it is stored in the variable *DATATYPE*. If the user enters a wrong number, then a **while** loop is run which asks to enter the right response. This feedback continues till the user enters the right response (see lines 30-33). After the correct response is recorded, we use the function **extractETCdata** to extract the information from the particular file associated with the response in *DATATYPE*. This is done using the command **extractETCdata(DATYPE)** and the output of the function is stored in *oncETCmain*. We keep a copy of the stored information in *oncETCmain* and make a second copy in the subsequent line in *oncETC* (see line 34-35). This manuscript explains the code for retrieving 2nd order combination, only so as to set a platform for many who would be reading the article. Note, before the use of the function i.e. instantiation of the function, the function needs to be defined and initialized. We defined the function and named it. After that an instance of the function is used to get a certain result. One instance is **extractETCdata(1)** and another instance is **extractETCdata(2)**.

```

30 # Data extraction
31 DATATYPE <- readline("Choose a file to
32 process [1/2] \n
33 1 - ../data/onc2015280x2-A.txt \n
34 Genes down-regulated after ETC-159
35 treatment \n
36 2 - ../data/onc2015280x2-B.txt \n
37 Genes up-regulated after ETC-159
38 treatment \n
39 File number - ")
40 while(DATATYPE != "1" & DATATYPE != "2"){
41   DATATYPE <- readline("Type the kind of
42   data to be processed [1/2] - ")
43 }
44 oncETCmain <- extractETCdata(DATYPE)
45 oncETC <- oncETCmain

```

Of interest is the column containing the \log_2 fold change numerical point estimates that are stored in the variable *oncETC*. Since the information under this column is stored in the data frame, it needs to be converted into a matrix for further processing by sensitivity analysis package. For this, **as.matrix** function is used which takes in the object in *x* along with arguments *ncol* which asks for the number of columns into which the information needs to be divided and *byrow* being false stating that the information will not be lined up row wise, but column wise. The result of the transformation is stored in *y*. Next, respective column elements in *y* are allotted their gene names. This is achieved using *oncETC\$Genesymbol*. The rownames of *y* which depict the gene names are thus assigned. We also save the names of the genes in *factor.names* variable. The dimension or the size of *y* in terms of number of rows and number of columns is recorded using the function **dim** and the measurements are stored in *dim.y*. *dim.y[1]* contains the number of rows which implicitly defines the number of genes (stored in *no.genes*). The whole list of genes can be shown on the command prompt during the execution of the code via **cat(rownames(y))** (see lines 35-40).

```

35 y <- as.matrix(x = oncETC$logTwoFC,
    ncol = 1, byrow = FALSE)
36 rownames(y) <- oncETC$Genesymbol
37 factor.names <- oncETC$Genesymbol
38 dim.y <- dim(y)
39 no.genes <- dim.y[1]
40 cat(rownames(y))

```

Next, the user is asked which gene the user would like to investigate and the response is stored in *geneName*. Also, since the pipeline is about investigating combinations, we need to input the number of combinations we are interested in. For this, a similar query is asked and the value is stored in the variable *k*. Since it is in the character format, it needs to be converted into a numerical format and that is done using **as.numeric** function. The **cat** function helps in displaying messages to ease the user to understand what is happening while execution of the program. The combinations that can be generated from *k* genes, out of the total number of genes *no.genes* is computed using **combn**. This returns a two dimensional matrix to **geneComb** whose number of columns represent the total number of combinations, i.e **dim(geneComb[2])** (see lines 41-47).

```

41 geneName <- readline("\nEnter name of
gene to be evaluated - ")
42 # Regarding combinations
43 ANSWER <- readline("nCk - choosing k - ")
44 k = as.numeric(ANSWER)
45 cat("choosing ",k," out of the",
    no.genes," genes!\n---\n")
46 geneComb <- combn(no.genes,k)
47 no.geneComb <- dim(geneComb)[2]

```

Next, initialization of the variables needs to be done for processing of the data. A series of list data structure is initialized and names are assigned to each new list as

shown from lines 49 to 60. These are the variables where the sensitivity indices will be stored. *siNames* contains the names of the indices which the search engine uses and the user can pick any one of them for computation. Line 63 prompts the user to enter the name of the sensitivity index, after looking at displayed list in the command on line 62. This name is stored in the variable *varName*. Next, we search for the pattern (stored in *varName*) in some of the Sobol index names and if the user has chosen a sobol sensitivity index, then *ISSOBOL* is assigned to a true value. This will be used and explained later on (see lines 49-66).

```

48 # some initializations
49 sensiFdiv.TV <- list()
50 sensiFdiv.KL <- list()
51 sensiFdiv.Chi2 <- list()
52 sensiFdiv.Hellinger <- list()
53 sensiHSIC.rbf <- list()
54 sensiHSIC.linear <- list()
55 sensiHSIC.laplace <- list()
56 SB.jansen <- list()
57 SB.2002 <- list()
58 SB.2007 <- list()
59 SB.martinez <- list()
60 SBL <- list()
61 siNames <- c("Fdiv.TV", "Fdiv.KL",
              "Fdiv.Chi2", "Fdiv.Hellinger", "HSIC.rbf",
              "HSIC.linear", "HSIC.laplace", "SB.2002",
              "SB.2007", "SB.jansen", "SB.martinez", "SBL")
62 cat("Types of SA - ", siNames, "\n")
63 varName <- readline("Enter a type of SA - ")
64 ISSOBOL <- FALSE
65 if(length(grep(varName, "SB.2002"))!= 0 |
      length(grep(varName, "SB.2007"))!= 0 |
      length(grep(varName, "SB.jansen"))!= 0 |
      length(grep(varName, "SB.martinez"))!= 0
      | length(grep(varName, "SBL"))!= 0){
      ISSOBOL <- TRUE
66 }

```

Regarding the generation of distribution of numerical point measurements, it is important to specify the number of samples. The user is usually given a choice as shown in line 67 (here commented). However, for exercise purpose, we set the value of number of samples to be $n = 10$. Next, the function for generating distribution of size 9 per gene measurement is used and the output is converted into a data frame using the function **data.frame**. This data frame is then stored in variable *disty* or distribution of *y*. We again save the number of samples as an extra using the **dim** function, in a variable **no.Samples** (see lines 67-71).

```

67 # n <- as.numeric(readline("Enter number of

```

```

    samples for distribution (odd numeric) - ")
68 n <- 9
69 disty <- data.frame(gdfetppv(n,t(y)))
70 no.Samples <- dim(disty)[1]
71 cat("generating sample combinations!\n")

```

The **apply** function is one of the important functions in R language and widely used for vector programming. It is important here in the sense that we need to compute the indices for combinations of factors. The arguments for **apply** take in a matrix, the indicator for a vector in a matrix over which a function will be applied. Here we see that *geneComb* is the matrix containing the combinations of genes; *MARGIN* with an indicator 2 means the columns of *geneComb* will be worked upon by the function **genSampleComb** in the variable *FUN*. Thus the function **apply** will apply the function **genSampleComb** to the columns of the matrix *geneComb*. The function **genSampleComb** in line 12, takes in a column of the matrix *geneComb* and returns the *k* distributions that are stored in the matrix *disty*. So, if *k* is 2, then the number of rows in *geneComb* will be 2. These 2 elements associated with a particular column in *geneComb* will contain the gene numbers in a list of genes. During the application of the **apply** function, *yCol* stores a column of *geneComb* and uses **genSampleComb** to generate *disty[yCol]*, a $n \times k$ matrix, where *n* is number of samples and *k* is the number of elements in combination. The procedure is applied to all columns of *geneComb*, for this. (see line 72).

```

72 distyN <- apply(X = geneComb, MARGIN = 2,
    FUN = genSampleComb)

```

Next, the combinatorial distributions stored in *distyN* are processed to segregate the gene combinations that contain the particular gene of interest defined by the user from a list of gene, in *geneName*. List variables are defined and to find combinations containing *geneName*, a **for** loop is executed where the iterator iterates through the total number of C_k^n combinations. For each of the combination contained in **names(distyN[i])**, if *geneName* is found to be existing, then the distribution containing *geneName* and another gene in *distyN[i]* is stored in *x.S*, a list. For every such identification, a counter *cnt* is incremented. Finally, after all combinations have been found which contain *geneName*, the final *cnt* is assigned to number of selected gene combinations *no.slgeneComb* (see lines 73-85).

```

73 # Sample with replicates
74 x.S <- list()
75 x.Sfh <- list()
76 x.Ssh <- list()
77 cnt <- 0
78 for(i in 1:no.geneComb){
79   if(geneName %in% names(distyN[[i]])){
80     cnt <- cnt + 1
81     x.S[[cnt]] <- distyN[[i]]
82   }
83 }

```

```

84 }
85 no.slgeneComb <- cnt

```

Usually a user will be asked about the total number of iterations for which the sensitivity indices will be generated. This is done to get an average sensitivity index score which is then used for ranking of the combinations. For demonstration purpose, we set the iteration number to $itrNo = 50$. The **for** loops the iterator itr for 50 iterations. Every iteration, the number of iteration is displayed at the start of the **for** loop. The samples need to be shuffled every time in order to have variation so that the mean of the sensitivity indices can be generated. This can be done by using the function **sample** which take a range of values from 1 to $no.Samples$ and the size of the sample is set to $no.Samples$. The shuffled samples are stored in $sample.index$. $idx.fh$ and $idx.sh$ are used to divide the sample into two halves, in case one is using Sobol method for generating sensitivity indices. Next, if the method used is Sobol or a variant of the same, as indicated by *ISSOBOL*, then shuffling of the samples in combination happens. This shuffling is done in lines 99-100, for all combinations, i.e j from 1 to $no.slgeneComb$. For, non Sobol based methods, the shuffling is simple as shown in line 104.

```

86 # itrNo <- as.numeric(readline("Number
    of iterations for averaged ranking - "))
87 itrNo <- 50
88 hmean <- list()
89 for(itr in 1:itrNo){
90   # disty <- data.frame(gdfetppv(n,yt))
91   # distyN can be replaced with x.S also

92   cat("generating for sample - ", itr, "\n")
93   sample.index <- sample(x = 1:no.Samples,
    size = no.Samples)
94   idx.fh <- sample.index[1:(no.Samples/2)]
95   idx.sh <- sample.index[((no.Samples/2)+1)
    :no.Samples]

96   # Shuffle the samples
97   if(ISSOBOL){
98     for(j in 1:no.slgeneComb){
99       x.Sfh[[j]] <- x.S[[j]][idx.fh,]
100      x.Ssh[[j]] <- x.S[[j]][idx.sh,]
101    }
102   }else{
103     for(j in 1:no.slgeneComb){
104       x.S[[j]] <- x.S[[j]][sample.index,]
105     }
106   }

```

Once the samples for the combinations have been stored in $x.S$, it is time to generate the sensitivity indices. To generate a sensitivity index of a particular type, the user has

to specify the name of the sensitivity index. This has already been done earlier and the name is stored in *varName*. What follows is a series of condition tests using the **if ... else** to know which type of sensitivity method needs to be taken into account and necessary method to be initiated to generate the indices. One of the approach would be to use **grep** function which searches for a pattern in *varName*. If the pattern exists, then the length of the finding would not be zero. When this condition holds, then a particular index associated with the pattern is initiated. So, if "TV" is the pattern and it found to be in the *varName*, then f-divergence method Csiszár et al. (1967) with a Total variation distance $|t - 1|$ needs to be initiated. The short explanation on the theoretical principles of density and variance based methods has been explained in Sinha (2017a). Here we concentrate on the flow of the code. In line 109, we define and initialize a new variable *FdivTV*. After some displays on the screen, **lapply** is used on *x.S*. **lapply** returns a list of the same length as *x.S*, each element of which is the result of applying function **sensiFdiv** to the corresponding element of *x.S*. Additionally, since the sensitivity method uses a model function, we use extra arguments in the **lapply** function, like *model = new.fun; nboot = 0* and *conf = 0.95*. This **new.fun** has earlier been defined in the beginning of the code. So, **lapply** generates sensitivity indices for each of the matrices containing a specific gene combination using the **new.fun** via **sensiFdiv**. The result is stored in a variable *h*. Since we know that **lapply** will generate sensitivity indices for each of the matrices in *x.S*, thus each combination has an associated sensitivity that is stored in *h[[p]]\$\$original*. We bind this to the variable *FdivTV* (see lines 108-113).

Next, since the **for** loop in line 89 works for many iterations, we need to store the sensitivity index computed in this iteration in a certain variable. This is done in *sensiFdiv.TV[[itr]]*, definition of which was done in line 49. Also, if this is the first iteration, then we define the file name based on the data that is being used and the iteration (see lines 115-117).

```

107 # itr <- 1
108 if(length(grep("TV",varName))!= 0){
109   FdivTV <- c()
110   cat("computing estimate different
      indices ... \n")
111   cat("Fdiv SA - TV\n")
112   h <- lapply(x.S, sensiFdiv,
      model = new.fun, fdiv = "TV",
      nboot = 0, conf = 0.95)
113   for(p in 1:no.slgeneComb){
      FdivTV <- cbind(FdivTV,
      h[[p]]$$original)
    }
114   sensiFdiv.TV[[itr]] <- FdivTV
115   if(DATATYPE == "1" & itr == 1){
      filename <- paste("order-",k,"-",
      geneName,
      "-DR-A-ETC-T-fdiv-tv-mean.Rdata",

```

```

        sep = "")
116   }else if(DATATYPE == "2" & itr == 1){
        filename <- paste("order-",k,"-",
        geneName,
        "-UR-A-ETC-T-fdiv-tv-mean.Rdata",
        sep = "")
117   }

```

The next series of conditions deals with the different methods in a similar manner as explained for lines 108-117. Lines 118-130 talk about f-divergence method Csiszár et al. (1967) with a Kullback-Leibler divergence $-\log_e(t)$.

```

118   }else if(length(grep("KL",varName))
        != 0){
119     FdivKL <- c()
120     cat("computing estimate different
        indices ... \n")
121     cat("Fdiv SA - KL\n")
122     h <- lapply(x.S, sensiFdiv,
        model = new.fun, fdiv = "KL",
        nboot = 0, conf = 0.95)
123     for(p in 1:no.slgeneComb){
124       FdivKL <- cbind(FdivKL,
        h[[p]]$$original)
125     }
125     sensiFdiv.KL[[itr]] <- FdivKL
126     if(DATATYPE == "1" & itr == 1){
127       filename <- paste("order-",k,"-",
        geneName,
        "-DR-A-ETC-T-fdiv-kl-mean.Rdata",
        sep = "")
128     }else if(DATATYPE == "2" & itr == 1){
129       filename <- paste("order-",k,"-",
        geneName,
        "-UR-A-ETC-T-fdiv-kl-mean.Rdata",
        sep = "")
130     }

```

Lines 131-144 talk about f-divergence method Csiszár et al. (1967) with a χ^2 distance $t^2 - 1$.

```

131   }else if(length(grep("Chi2",varName))
        != 0){
132     FdivChi2 <- c()
133     cat("computing estimate different

```

```

    indices ... \n")
134   cat("Fdiv SA - Chi2\n")
135   h <- lapply(x.S, sensiFdiv,
    model = new.fun, fdiv = "Chi2",
    nboot = 0, conf = 0.95)
136   for(p in 1:no.slgeneComb){
137     FdivChi2 <- cbind(FdivChi2,
    h[[p]]$$original)
138   }
139   sensiFdiv.Chi2[[itr]] <- FdivChi2
140   if(DATATYPE == "1" & itr == 1){
141     filename <- paste("order-",k,"-",
    geneName,
    "-DR-A-ETC-T-fdiv-chi2-mean.Rdata",
    sep = "")
142   }else if(DATATYPE == "2" & itr == 1){
143     filename <- paste("order-",k,"-",
    geneName,
    "-UR-A-ETC-T-fdiv-chi2-mean.Rdata",
    sep = "")
144   }

```

Lines 145-158 talk about f-divergence method Csiszár et al. (1967) with a Hellinger distance $(\sqrt{t}-1)^2$.

```

145   }else if(length(grep("Hellinger",varName))
    != 0){
146     FdivHellinger <- c()
147     cat("computing estimate different
    indices ... \n")
148     cat("Fdiv SA - Hellinger\n")
149     h <- lapply(x.S, sensiFdiv,
    model = new.fun, fdiv = "Hellinger",
    nboot = 0, conf = 0.95)
150     for(p in 1:no.slgeneComb){
151       FdivHellinger <- cbind(FdivHellinger,
    h[[p]]$$original)
152     }
153     sensiFdiv.Hellinger[[itr]]
    <- FdivHellinger
154     if(DATATYPE == "1" & itr == 1){
155       filename <- paste("order-",k,"-",
    geneName,
    "-DR-A-ETC-T-fdiv-hellinger-mean.Rdata",
    sep = "")
156     }else if(DATATYPE == "2" & itr == 1){

```

```

157     filename <- paste("order-",k,"-",
        geneName,
        "-UR-A-ETC-T-fdiv-hellinger-mean.Rdata",
        sep = "")
158   }

```

Da Veiga (2015) recently proposed a new set of dependence measures using kernel methods. These also, have been implemented in Pujol et al. (2016). The following contains variants of different kernels involved in computing the sensitivity indices. Lines 159-172 show similar execution code as above with changes in some of the arguments in the **lapply** function. Here, the "rbf" or radial basis function is used within **sensiHSIC**.

```

159   }else if(length(grep("rbf",varName))
        != 0){
160     HSICrbf <- c()
161     cat("computing estimate different
        indices ... \n")
162     cat("HSIC SA - rbf kernel \n")
163     h <- lapply(x.S, sensiHSIC,
        model = new.fun, kernelX = "rbf",
        paramX = NA, kernelY = "rbf",
        paramY = NA, conf = 0.95)
164     for(p in 1:no.slgeneComb){
165       HSICrbf <- cbind(HSICrbf,
        h[[p]]$$original)
166     }
167     sensiHSIC.rbf[[itr]] <- HSICrbf
168     if(DATATYPE == "1" & itr == 1){
169       filename <- paste("order-",k,"-",
        geneName,
        "-DR-A-ETC-T-hsic-rbf-mean.Rdata",
        sep = "")
170     }else if(DATATYPE == "2" & itr == 1){
171       filename <- paste("order-",k,"-",
        geneName,
        "-UR-A-ETC-T-hsic-rbf-mean.Rdata",
        sep = "")
172     }

```

Lines 173-186 show similar execution code as above with changes in some of the arguments in the **lapply** function. Here, the linear function is used.

```

173   }else if(length(grep("linear",varName))
        != 0){
174     HSIClinear <- c()
175     cat("computing estimate different

```

```

    indices ... \n")
176   cat("HSIC SA - linear kernel\n")
177   h <- lapply(x.S, sensiHSIC,
    model = new.fun, kernelX = "linear",
    paramX = NA, kernelY = "linear",
    paramY = NA, conf = 0.95)
178   for(p in 1:no.slgeneComb){
179     HSIClinear <- cbind(HSIClinear,
    h[[p]]$$original)
180   }
181   sensiHSIC.linear[[itr]] <- HSIClinear
182   if(DATATYPE == "1" & itr == 1){
183     filename <- paste("order-",k,"-",
    geneName,
    "-DR-A-ETC-T-hsic-linear-mean.Rdata",
    sep = "")
184   }else if(DATATYPE == "2" & itr == 1){
185     filename <- paste("order-",k,"-",
    geneName,
    "-UR-A-ETC-T-hsic-linear-mean.Rdata",
    sep = "")
186   }

```

Lines 187-200 show similar execution code as above with changes in some of the arguments in the **lapply** function. Here, the **laplace** function is used.

```

187 }else if(length(grep("laplace",varName))
    != 0){
188   HSIClaplace <- c()
189   cat("computing estimate different
    indices ... \n")
190   cat("HSIC SA - laplace kernel\n")
191   h <- lapply(x.S, sensiHSIC,
    model = new.fun, kernelX = "laplace",
    paramX = NA, kernelY = "laplace",
    paramY = NA, conf = 0.95)
192   for(p in 1:no.slgeneComb){
193     HSIClaplace <- cbind(HSIClaplace,
    h[[p]]$$original)
194   }
195   sensiHSIC.laplace[[itr]] <- HSIClaplace
196   if(DATATYPE == "1" & itr == 1){
197     filename <- paste("order-",k,"-",
    geneName,
    "-DR-A-ETC-T-hsic-laplace-mean.Rdata",
    sep = "")

```

```

198     }else if(DATATYPE == "2" & itr == 1){
199         filename <- paste("order-",k,"-",
                geneName,
                "-UR-A-ETC-T-hsic-laplace-mean.Rdata",
                sep = "")
200     }

```

Finally, we come to the section, where variants of the Sobol function have been encoded. It is here that the use of divided samples *X.Sfh* and *X.Ssh* comes to play. We do not use the **lapply** function. Instead, the Sobol' (1990) variants are encoded using name specific function (see below). Lines 201-214 show similar execution code as above, but using **soboljansen**.

```

201     }else if(length(grep("jansen",varName))
                != 0){
202         SBLjansen <- c()
203         cat("computing estimate different
                indices ... \n")
204         cat("Sobol Jansen SA \n")
205         for(p in 1:no.slgeneComb){
206             h <- soboljansen(model = new.fun,
                X1 = t(x.Sfh[[p]]),
                X2 = t(x.Ssh[[p]]), conf = 0.95)
207             SBLjansen <- cbind(SBLjansen,
                c(h$$original, h$T$original))
208         }
209         SB.jansen[[itr]] <- SBLjansen
210         if(DATATYPE == "1" & itr == 1){
211             filename <- paste("order-",k,"-",
                geneName,
                "-DR-A-ETC-T-sb-jansen-mean.Rdata",
                sep = "")
212         }else if(DATATYPE == "2" & itr == 1){
213             filename <- paste("order-",k,"-",
                geneName,
                "-UR-A-ETC-T-sb-jansen-mean.Rdata",
                sep = "")
214         }

```

Lines 215-228 show similar execution code as above, but using **sobol2002**.

```

215     }else if(length(grep("2002",varName))
                != 0){
216         SBL2002 <- c()
217         cat("computing estimate different
                indices ... \n")
218         cat("Sobol 2002 SA \n")

```

```

219     for(p in 1:no.slgeneComb){
220         h <- sobol2002(model = new.fun,
                X1 = t(x.Sfh[[p]]),
                X2 = t(x.Ssh[[p]]), conf = 0.95)
221     SBL2002 <- cbind(SBL2002,
                c(h$$original, h$T$original))
222     }
223     SB.2002[[itr]] <- SBL2002
224     if(DATATYPE == "1" & itr == 1){
225         filename <- paste("order-",k,"-",
                geneName,
                "-DR-A-ETC-T-sb-2002-mean.Rdata",
                sep = "")
226     }else if(DATATYPE == "2" & itr == 1){
227         filename <- paste("order-",k,"-",
                geneName,
                "-UR-A-ETC-T-sb-2002-mean.Rdata",
                sep = "")
228     }

```

Lines 229-242 show similar execution code as above, but using **sobol2007**.

```

229     }else if(length(grep("2007",varName))
                != 0){
230         SBL2007 <- c()
231         cat("computing estimate different
                indices ...\n")
232         cat("Sobol 2007 SA\n")
233         for(p in 1:no.slgeneComb){
234             h <- sobol2007(model = new.fun,
                    X1 = t(x.Sfh[[p]]),
                    X2 = t(x.Ssh[[p]]), conf = 0.95)
235             SBL2007 <- cbind(SBL2007,
                    c(h$$original, h$T$original))
236         }
237         SB.2007[[itr]] <- SBL2007
238         if(DATATYPE == "1" & itr == 1){
239             filename <- paste("order-",k,"-",
                    geneName,
                    "-DR-A-ETC-T-sb-2007-mean.Rdata",
                    sep = "")
240         }else if(DATATYPE == "2" & itr == 1){
241             filename <- paste("order-",k,"-",
                    geneName,
                    "-UR-A-ETC-T-sb-2007-mean.Rdata",
                    sep = "")
242         }

```

Lines 243-256 show similar execution code as above, but using **sobolmartinez**.

```
243     }else if(length(grep("martinez",varName))
244         != 0){
245         SBLmartinez <- c()
246         cat("computing estimate different
247             indices ...\n")
248         cat("Sobol Martinez SA\n")
249         for(p in 1:no.slgeneComb){
250             h <- sobolmartinez(model = new.fun,
251                 X1 = t(x.Sfh[[p]]),
252                 X2 = t(x.Ssh[[p]]), conf = 0.95)
253             SBLmartinez <- cbind(SBLmartinez,
254                 c(h$$original, h$T$original))
255         }
256         SB.martinez[[itr]] <- SBLmartinez
257         if(DATATYPE == "1" & itr == 1){
258             filename <- paste("order-",k,"-",
259                 geneName,
260                 "-DR-A-ETC-T-sb-martinez-mean.Rdata",
261                 sep = "")
262         }else if(DATATYPE == "1" & itr == 1){
263             filename <- paste("order-",k,"-",
264                 geneName,
265                 "-UR-A-ETC-T-sb-martinez-mean.Rdata",
266                 sep = "")
267         }
```

Lines 257-272 show similar execution code as above, but using **sobol**.

```
257     }else if(length(grep("SBL",varName))
258         != 0){
259         sbl <- c()
260         cat("computing estimate different
261             indices ...\n")
262         cat("SBL SA\n")
263         for(p in 1:no.slgeneComb){
264             h <- sobol(model = new.fun,
265                 X1 = t(x.Sfh[[p]]),
266                 X2 = t(x.Ssh[[p]]), order = 1,
267                 conf = 0.95)
268             sbl <- cbind(SBL, c(h$$original,
269                 h$T$original))
270         }
271         SBL[[itr]] <- sbl
272         if(DATATYPE == "1" & itr == 1){
273             filename <- paste("order-",k,"-",
```

```

        geneName,
        "-DR-A-ETC-T-sbl-mean.Rdata",
        sep = "")
268   }else if(DATATYPE == "2" & itr == 1){
269     filename <- paste("order-",k,"-",
        geneName,
        "-UR-A-ETC-T-sbl-mean.Rdata",
        sep = "")
270   }
271 }
272 }

```

Once the indices have been generated, they need to be stored in a file for further processing. The following set of lines help in saving the work, were the function **save** is used and variables *no.slgeneComb*, *x.S* and the respective sensitivity indices related to *varName* is stored in the *filename*.

```

273 if(length(grep("TV",varName))!= 0){
274   save(no.slgeneComb, x.S,
        sensiFdiv.TV, file = filename)
275 }else if(length(grep("KL",varName))
        != 0){
276   save(no.slgeneComb, x.S,
        sensiFdiv.KL, file = filename)
277 }else if(length(grep("Chi2",varName))
        != 0){
278   save(no.slgeneComb, x.S,
        sensiFdiv.Chi2, file = filename)
279 }else if(length(grep("Hellinger",varName))
        != 0){
280   save(no.slgeneComb, x.S,
        sensiFdiv.Hellinger, file = filename)
281 }else if(length(grep("rbf",varName))
        != 0){
282   save(no.slgeneComb, x.S,
        sensiHSIC.rbf, file = filename)
283 }else if(length(grep("linear",varName))
        != 0){
284   save(no.slgeneComb, x.S,
        sensiHSIC.linear, file = filename)
285 }else if(length(grep("laplace",varName))
        != 0){

```

```

286     save(no.slgeneComb, x.S,
          SB.jansen, file = filename)
287 }else if(length(grep("2002",varName))
          != 0){
289     save(no.slgeneComb, x.S,
          SB.2002, file = filename)
290 }else if(length(grep("2007",varName))
          != 0){
291     save(no.slgeneComb, x.S,
          SB.2007, file = filename)
292 }else if(length(grep("martinez",varName))
          != 0){
293     save(no.slgeneComb, x.S,
          SB.martinez, file = filename)
294 }else if(length(grep("SBL",varName))
          != 0){
295     save(no.slgeneComb, x.S,
          SBL, file = filename)
296 }

```

This ends the coding part of estimating sensitivity indices. Once the indices are ready they can be used in various ways for evaluation of the combinations. Here, we use one of the ways to ranking these scores. However, not that there is no one definite rule to say that one has to rank in this way only. It depends on the research to decide what method one is employing for ranking. We use the SVM^{Rank} algorithm by Joachims (2006). Though complex in nature, it does a fair job in ranking the scores. The use of a machine learning approach is also made available to see how the learning algorithms play critical role in revealing unknown/untested combinatorial hypotheses. Other reasons of using these will be stated later on.

5.3.2. Exercise

At this stage, it would be great to see how the two codes on extracting data and generating indices works out. The readers are requested to generate the different types of indices based on their choice and see what comparisons can be made using the different indices. Also try the following exercises -

1. Generate HSIC rbf indices for 2^{nd} order combinations for downregulated AXIN2. What does the combination of AXIN2 with another factor that has lowest score mean?
2. Generate FDiv KL indices for 2^{nd} order combinations for downregulated MYC. What does the combination of MYC with another factor that has highest score mean?
3. Generate HSIC laplace indices for 2^{nd} order combinations for downregulated NKD1. What does the combination of NKD1 with another factor that has score in the middle mean?

4. Generate FDiv TV indices for 2^{nd} order combinations for downregulated CDAN1. What does the combination of CDAN1 with another factor that has score at 100 position in ascending order mean?
5. Generate Sobol indices for 2^{nd} order combinations for downregulated MINA. How many kinds of indices can you generate? Compare them for a particular combination!
6. Generate Sobol jansen indices for 2^{nd} order combinations for downregulated MINA. How many kinds of indices can you generate? Compare them for two different combinations!
7. Generate Sobol martinez indices for 2^{nd} order combinations for downregulated MINA. How many kinds of indices can you generate? Compare them for 20 different combinations!
8. Generate Sobol 2002 and 2007 indices for 2^{nd} order combinations for downregulated MINA. How many kinds of indices can you generate? Compare Sobol 2002 vs Sobol 2007
9. Compare HSIC rbf, HSIC laplace, FDiv TV, FDiv KL, Sobol, Sobol jansen, Sobol martinez, Sobol 2002 and 2007 indices for down regulated LGR5-RNF43.

5.4. Ranking & Sorting

5.4.1. Description of SVM-Results-S-mean.R

This part of the code is the last in the pipeline that works on the generated sensitivity indices. The code is in the file SVMRank-Results-S-mean.R. It ranks the sensitivity indices using a machine learning algorithm. We go through this part of the code and will then come back to why's and why not's. Lines 1-16 are basic data processing techniques and some formalities that need to be done before we begin on the ranking part. So, by now, it should be expected the reader is able to work through the line and understand what is happening if a following line is being executed, at least, theoretically.

```

1  DATATYPE <- readline("Choose a file
   to process [1/2] \n
2  1 - ../data/onc2015280x2-A.txt \n
3  Genes down-regulated after ETC-159
   treatment \n
4  2 - ../data/onc2015280x2-B.txt \n
5  Genes up-regulated after ETC-159
   treatment \n
6  File number - ")
7  while(DATATYPE != "1" & DATATYPE != "2"){
8    DATATYPE <- readline("Type the kind of
   data to be processed - ")
9  }
10
11  CHOOSE <- as.numeric(readline("pick a
   numeric for k in nCk - "))

```

```

12 k <- as.numeric(CHOOSE)
13
14 geneName <- readline("Please enter the
   name of the gene to be processed - ")
15 siNames <- c("Fdiv.TV", "Fdiv.KL",
   "Fdiv.Chi2", "Fdiv.Hellinger", "HSIC.rbf",
   "HSIC.linear", "HSIC.laplace", "SB.2002",
   "SB.2007", "SB.jansen", "SB.martinez",
   "SBL")
16 sa.name <- readline("Please enter the
   name of the proposed SA from above
   list - ")

```

We stored the sensitivity indices in different files. These files need to be accessed in order for the procedure of ranking to be initiated. The following lines help retrieve the file names which can then be loaded into the R workspace from where it can be accessed easily. To retrieve the file name, the function **paste** is employed. Readers are encouraged to find how the **paste** function works. After the file name is constructed, the contents of the file are loaded using the **load** function, followed by the assignment of stored data into a variable *h*. Lines 17-113 show the code for various kinds of indices that a user can access, after using **paste** and **load**.

```

17 if(length(grep(sa.name, "Fdiv.TV"))
   != 0){
18   if(DATATYPE == "1"){
19     filename <- paste("order-", k, "-",
   geneName,
   "-DR-A-ETC-T-fdiv-tv-mean.Rdata",
   sep = "")
20   }else{
21     filename <- paste("order-", k, "-",
   geneName,
   "-UR-A-ETC-T-fdiv-tv-mean.Rdata",
   sep = "")
22   }
23   load(filename)
24   h <- sensiFdiv.TV
25 }else if(length(grep(sa.name, "Fdiv.KL"))
   != 0){
26   if(DATATYPE == "1"){
27     filename <- paste("order-", k, "-",
   geneName,
   "-DR-A-ETC-T-fdiv-kl-mean.Rdata",
   sep = "")
28   }else{
29     filename <- paste("order-", k, "-",

```

```

        geneName,
        "-UR-A-ETC-T-fdiv-kl-mean.Rdata",
        sep = "")
30   }
31   load(filename)
32   h <- sensiFdiv.KL
33 }else if(length(grep(sa.name,"Fdiv.Chi2"))
    != 0){
34   if(DATATYPE == "1"){
35     filename <- paste("order-",k,"-",
        geneName,
        "-DR-A-ETC-T-fdiv-chi2-mean.Rdata",
        sep = "")
36   }else{
37     filename <- paste("order-",k,"-",
        geneName,
        "-UR-A-ETC-T-fdiv-chi2-mean.Rdata",
        sep = "")
38   }
39   load(filename)
40   h <- sensiFdiv.Chi2
41 }else if(length(grep(sa.name,"Fdiv.Hellinger"))
    != 0){
42   if(DATATYPE == "1"){
43     filename <- paste("order-",k,"-",
        geneName,
        "-DR-A-ETC-T-fdiv-hellinger-mean.Rdata",
        sep = "")
44   }else{
45     filename <- paste("order-",k,"-",
        geneName,
        "-UR-A-ETC-T-fdiv-hellinger-mean.Rdata",
        sep = "")
46   }
47   load(filename)
48   h <- sensiFdiv.Hellinger
49 }else if(length(grep(sa.name,"HSIC.rbf"))
    !=0){
50   if(DATATYPE == "1"){
51     filename <- paste("order-",k,"-",
        geneName,
        "-DR-A-ETC-T-hsic-rbf-mean.Rdata",
        sep = "")
52   }else{
53     filename <- paste("order-",k,"-",
        geneName,

```

```

        "-UR-A-ETC-T-hsic-rbf-mean.Rdata",
        sep = "")
54     }
55     load(filename)
56     h <- sensiHSIC.rbf
57 }else if(length(grep(sa.name,"HSIC.linear"))
    != 0){
58     if(DATATYPE == "1"){
59         filename <- paste("order-",k,"-",
            geneName,
            "-DR-A-ETC-T-hsic-linear-mean.Rdata",
            sep = "")
60     }else{
61         filename <- paste("order-",k,"-",
            geneName,
            "-UR-A-ETC-T-hsic-linear-mean.Rdata",
            sep = "")
62     }
63     load(filename)
64     h <- sensiHSIC.linear
65 }else if(length(grep(sa.name,"HSIC.laplace"))
    != 0){
66     if(DATATYPE == "1"){
67         filename <- paste("order-",k,"-",
            geneName,
            "-DR-A-ETC-T-hsic-laplace-mean.Rdata",
            sep = "")
68     }else{
69         filename <- paste("order-",k,"-",
            geneName,
            "-UR-A-ETC-T-hsic-laplace-mean.Rdata",
            sep = "")
70     }
71     load(filename)
72     h <- sensiHSIC.laplace
73 }else if(length(grep(sa.name,"SB.2002"))
    != 0){
74     if(DATATYPE == "1"){
75         filename <- paste("order-",k,"-",
            geneName,
            "-DR-A-ETC-T-sb-2002-mean.Rdata",
            sep = "")
76     }else{
77         filename <- paste("order-",k,"-",
            geneName,
            "-UR-A-ETC-T-sb-2002-mean.Rdata",

```

```

      sep = "")
78   }
79   load(filename)
80   h <- SB.2002
81 }else if(length(grep(sa.name,"SB.2007"))
      != 0){
82   if(DATATYPE == "1"){
83     filename <- paste("order-",k,"-",
      geneName,
      "-DR-A-ETC-T-sb-2007-mean.Rdata",
      sep = "")
84   }else{
85     filename <- paste("order-",k,"-",
      geneName,
      "-UR-A-ETC-T-sb-2007-mean.Rdata",
      sep = "")
86   }
87   load(filename)
88   h <- SB.2007
89 }else if(length(grep(sa.name,"SB.jansen"))
      != 0){
90   if(DATATYPE == "1"){
91     filename <- paste("order-",k,"-",
      geneName,
      "-DR-A-ETC-T-sb-jansen-mean.Rdata",
      sep = "")
92   }else{
93     filename <- paste("order-",k,"-",
      geneName,
      "-UR-A-ETC-T-sb-jansen-mean.Rdata",
      sep = "")
94   }
95   load(filename)
96   h <- SB.jansen
97 }else if(length(grep(sa.name,"SB.martinez"))
      != 0){
98   if(DATATYPE == "1"){
99     filename <- paste("order-",k,"-",
      geneName,
      "-DR-A-ETC-T-sb-martinez-mean.Rdata",
      sep = "")
100  }else{
101  filename <- paste("order-",k,"-",
      geneName,
      "-UR-A-ETC-T-sb-martinez-mean.Rdata",
      sep = "")

```

```

102   }
103   load(filename)
104   h <- SB.martinez
105 }else if(length(grep(sa.name,"SBL"))
      != 0){
106   if(DATATYPE == "1"){
107     filename <- paste("order-",k,"-",
      geneName,
      "-DR-A-ETC-T-sbl-mean.Rdata",
      sep = "")
108   }else{
109     filename <- paste("order-",k,"-",
      geneName,
      "-UR-A-ETC-T-sbl-mean.Rdata",
      sep = "")
110   }
111   load(filename)
112   h <- SBL
113 }

```

Once the indicies that have to be worked on have been put in h , the indicies need to be averaged. For demonstration purpose, we average only 2 iterations and see how things turn out. However, we need to understand how the data is stored in h . Figure 3 shows a screen shot of how element of h looks. $h[[25]]$ is the 25th element and is a matrix of size 2×2743 . 2 is the number of elements in a combination under consideration and 2743 are the total number of distinct 2nd order combinations. We exploit this view of h to compute the means of for all elements of a combination and over all distinct combinations. This is done in the **for** loops below in which p iterates over elements of combination and itr iterates over the total number of iterations. Thus $h[[itr]][p,]$ between the two nested **for** loops considers the p^{th} row of itr^{th} matrix in h . Then, r binds all the $h[[1]][p,]$, $h[[2]][p,]$, ..., $h[[itrNo]][p,]$, using **rbind**. After exiting the inner loop, we use the **apply** function to r matrix over the columns (i.e the distinct combinations) with a function **mean**. Thus we get a vector of mean values of sensitivity index for each distinct combination over all iterations, for the p^{th} element. This process is again repeated for the next p value. Finally, the vector of means are stacked in $S\text{Amean}$. Lines 114-124 show this coding below.

```

114 # Use this for averaged ranking
115 # itrNo <- 50
116 itrNo <- 2
117 SAmean <- c()
118 for(p in 1:k){
119   r <- c()
120   for(itr in 1:itrNo){
121     r <- rbind(h[[itr]][p,])
122   }

```


Figure 3: Screen shot of data loaded using `load` function and the assignment of the stored sensitivity indices to variable `h`.

```

123     SAmean <- rbind(SAmean, apply(X = r,
124       MARGIN = 2, mean))

```

Next, we format the data in the form that is suitable for the SVM^{rank} machine. The output of the next block of code can be depicted in figure 4. Note that it is a screen shot for how the data is saved for a 3rd order combination. I invite readers to decode the following block by themselves as an exercise.

```

125 # y <- SA
126 y <- SAmean
127 data <- c()
128 for(i in 1:no.slgeneComb){
129   z <- c()
130   z <- cbind(z,i)
131   for(j in 1:k){
132     z <- cbind(z,
133       paste(j,":",y[j,i],sep=""))

```

```

1 1:0.626364377309334 2:0.527505676513961 3:0.113762327838243
2 1:0.115627329301083 2:0.70140375947702 3:0.555882270527448
3 1:0.544876192378511 2:0.352285442741931 3:0.370635265560798
4 1:0.192361398371323 2:0.310239010742538 3:0.49204266288273
5 1:0.58285348514642 2:0.281413460065595 3:0.327493744822505
6 1:0.351034419102818 2:0.343384617420989 3:0.148505969101492
7 1:0.782560172370969 2:0.345140938098646 3:0.177258473888461
8 1:0.630907570829286 2:0.56855192811936 3:0.138584623911373
9 1:0.216195532101444 2:0.414543916226165 3:0.113980668309361
10 1:0.283895945186652 2:0.361780765317981 3:0.366435248118148
11 1:0.16287050503857 2:0.868613911042874 3:0.0989378976820292
12 1:0.561850003081091 2:0.541890862307686 3:0.23980018742167
13 1:0.277823319222624 2:0.410498428589253 3:0.149938817070323
14 1:0.639343729150494 2:0.210620804117997 3:0.318994509227185
15 1:0.579922798562767 2:0.169151589969098 3:0.505153429556521
16 1:0.255426206049244 2:0.19861791055204 3:0.603574373800882
17 1:0.638429174520452 2:0.210968681381445 3:0.31558414172227
18 1:0.308210498731067 2:0.315067213362584 3:0.369723298974591
19 1:0.232194144603514 2:0.0899698653586265 3:0.433147306693618
20 1:0.219438264672644 2:0.237701371516819 3:0.565164770668834
21 1:0.314375908725559 2:0.0610464637955092 3:0.626864567521388
22 1:0.714942050999006 2:0.315230485087249 3:0.117059293878145
23 1:0.181503219052467 2:0.208940762198194 3:0.566116193159678
24 1:0.344060825165414 2:0.274995877172336 3:0.464454457596415
25 1:0.531735675357153 2:0.329899209905158 3:0.162742316265039
26 1:0.403603998882616 2:0.557601792454423 3:0.346263613235206
27 1:0.249735943401084 2:0.200509610657229 3:0.583767751340706
28 1:0.473426972917293 2:0.134940754963889 3:0.633285486398736
29 1:0.400155830984346 2:0.491206008718229 3:0.103962327133218
30 1:0.22660716984713 2:0.632930663188795 3:0.369777827505766

```

Figure 4: Screen shot of data after transformation in lines 125-136. This is an example of 3rd order combination.

```

134     z <- cbind(z,"\n")
135     data <- rbind(data,z)
136   }

```

Next the file names for training, testing, model and prediction are built using paste (see lines 137-140). And finally, data is concatenated to the training and the testing files (see lines 141-142).

```

137   trnfl <- paste("svr-trn-order-",k,
138                 "-",geneName,".txt", sep = "")
138   tstfl <- paste("svr-tst-order-",k,
139                 "-",geneName,".txt", sep = "")
139   mdlfl <- paste("svr-mdl-order-",k,
140                 "-",geneName,".txt", sep = "")
140   predfl <- paste("svr-pred-order-",k,
141                  "-",geneName,".txt", sep = "")

141   cat(t(data),file=trnfl)
142   cat(t(data),file=tstfl)

```

We now come to the main part of the code which involves using the support vector ranking algorithm. Since it is a compiled executable file, it needs to be executed using a **system** command. However, before that, the command that needs to be executed must

be prepared in the right format. For this the **paste** command is used (see line 144). In the paste command *svm_rank_learn* takes in the *C* value in the form of $-c20$; $-#100$ to terminate svm-light QP subproblem optimization, if no progress after this number of iterations; $-n9$ number of new variables entering the working set in each svm-light iteration (default $n = q$): Set $n < q$ to prevent zig-zagging: We set n to 9 considering the number of samples generated from distribution; the training file and the model file. Finally we use the built up command in the **system** function (see line 145).

```
143 # svm rank learn on C value - 20
144 cmd <- paste(
      "../svm_rank/svm_rank_learn
      -c 20 -# 100 -n 9",trnfl,mdlfl,sep=" ")
145 system(command=cmd)
```

Similar format is used to classify the test file, once the model has been prepared using the *svm_rank_learn*. This is achieved using the *svm_rank_classify*. Note that when there is only one instance of each training data, then after the model is being built on it, for ranking purpose, we use the same training as testing file. This might sound strange at first view, however, the model should be able to rank the scores based of the original data. It is not a hard and fast rule to rank through SVMs but, here we show an example of the same. One can use a completely different algorithm also for the same set of training data. Ranking is done in the next lines 146-148.

```
146 # svm rank classify
147 cmd <- paste(
      "../svm_rank/svm_rank_classify",
      tstfl,mdlfl,predfl,sep=" ")
148 system(command=cmd)
```

Once the ranking is done, the data in the prediction file is stored in a variable via **read.table** function and later stored in an appropriate file. Again the file name need to be constructed. See lines 149-156.

```
149 # read predictions of rankings
150 dataScore <- read.table(predfl)

151 # save it in appropriate file
152 if(DATATYPE == "1"){
153   save(dataScore,file=paste("order-",k,
      "-SA-",sa.name,"-",geneName,
      "-rankingScore-mean-DR.R",sep=""))
154 }else{
155   save(dataScore,file=paste("order-",k,
      "-SA-",sa.name,"-",geneName,
      "-rankingScore-mean-UR.R",sep=""))
156 }
```

```

"x"
"1" "KIF22-CENPA"
"2" "NAT10-CENPA"
"3" "LRIG1-CENPA"
"4" "KIF20A-CENPA"
"5" "MKI67-CENPA"
"6" "HJURP-CENPA"
"7" "DKC1-CENPA"
"8" "CLDN2-CENPA"
"9" "MCM3-CENPA"
"10" "C11orf82-CENPA"
"11" "C1QBP-CENPA"
"12" "TYMS-CENPA"
"13" "BIRC5-CENPA"
"14" "KIF4A-CENPA"
"15" "CIT-CENPA"
"16" "WHSC1-CENPA"
"17" "SLC12A2-CENPA"
"18" "AURKA-CENPA"
"19" "KIF11-CENPA"
"20" "APEX1-CENPA"
"21" "NEK2-CENPA"
"22" "PRC1-CENPA"
"23" "LIG1-CENPA"
"24" "UHRF1-CENPA"
"25" "CHEK1-CENPA"
"26" "NDC80-CENPA"
"27" "NPM3-CENPA"
"28" "MCM2-CENPA"
"29" "PLEKHB1-CENPA"

```

Figure 5: Screen shot of ranked combinations.

5.4.2. Exercise

Please download the *SVM^{rank}* and as instructed on the website of Joachims (2006), compile the same to get executable files.

5.4.3. Sorting

Finally, we sort the predicted results. These are expressed in the last block from lines 157-172. *dataScore* that contained the predictions is sorted using the **sort** function and the indices of the sorted values is also returned (see line 159). Next, using the **for** loop we arrange the names of the combinations in a sorted order using the sorted index in line 159. These sorted combinations are appended in *sortedGenecomb* (see lines 161-167). Finally, we store these results according to the type of data we are dealing with.

```

157 # sort the predicted scores
158 cat("sorting in ascending order
      - top is lowest in ranking")
159 dataScore <- sort(dataScore$V1,
                    index.return=TRUE)
160 noCombs <- length(dataScore$ix)

161 # arrange the combinations by ranking
162 sortedGenecomb <- c()

```

```

R Console
~/Science/Sabbatical/DynamicsOfWnt/codeFor-virData
Type 'license()' or 'licence()' for distribution details.

Natural language support but running in an English locale

R is a collaborative project with many contributors.
Type 'contributors()' for more information and
'citation()' on how to cite R or R packages in publications.

Type 'demo()' for some demos, 'help()' for on-line help, or
'help.start()' for an HTML browser interface to help.
Type 'q()' to quit R.

During startup - Warning messages:
1: Setting LC_CTYPE failed, using "C"
2: Setting LC_COLLATE failed, using "C"
3: Setting LC_TIME failed, using "C"
4: Setting LC_MESSAGES failed, using "C"
5: Setting LC_MONETARY failed, using "C"
[R.app GUI 1.70 (7375) x86_64-apple-darwin15.6.0]

WARNING: You're using a non-UTF8 locale, therefore only ASCII characters will work.
Please read R for Mac OS X FAQ (see Help) section 9 and adjust your system preferences accordingly.
[History restored from /Users/shriprakashsinha/.Rapp.history]

> setwd("Science/Sabbatical/DynamicsOfWnt/codeFor-virData/")
> source("extractETCdata.R")
> extractETCdata(1)
Called from: extractETCdata(1)
Browse[1]>
debug at extractETCdata.R#3: if (data.type == 1) {
  filename <- "../data/onc2015280x2-A.txt"
} else {
  filename <- "../data/onc2015280x2-B.txt"
}
Browse[2]>
debug at extractETCdata.R#4: filename <- "../data/onc2015280x2-A.txt"
Browse[2]>
debug at extractETCdata.R#9: lineCnt <- system(command = paste("wc -l ", filename, sep = ""),
  intern = TRUE)
Browse[2]>

```

Figure 6: Screen shot of browser output in the white patch in the screen shoot.

```

163   for(i in 1:noCombs){
164     idx <- dataScore$ix[i]
165     z <- capture.output(cat(
      names(x.S[[idx]]), sep="--"))

```

```

166     sortedGenecomb <- c(sortedGenecomb, z)
167   }
168   if(DATATYPE == "1"){
169     write.table(sortedGenecomb,
                  file=paste("order-",k,"-SA-",
                             sa.name,"-",geneName,
                             "-ranking-mean-DR.txt",sep=""))
170   }else{
171     write.table(sortedGenecomb,
                  file=paste("order-",k,"-SA-",
                             sa.name,"-",geneName,
                             "-ranking-mean-UR.txt",sep=""))
172   }

```

The sorted combinations look like that in figure 5. This finishes the general framework of the pipeline.

6. Code surgery via browser scalpel

R provides with a **browser** function which can help one to see the contents of the variables and intermediate outputs once the execution of the code has begun. The function is like a scalpel which helps dissect the entire code as the execution proceeds one step at a time. Various functionalities exist to use browser function. These can be seen by typing **?browser** at the command prompt. Briefly -

- **c** exit the browser and continue execution at the next statement.
- **f** finish execution of the current loop or function help print this list of commands.
- **n** evaluate the next statement, stepping over function calls. For byte compiled functions interrupted by browser calls, n is equivalent to c.
- **s** evaluate the next statement, stepping into function calls. Again, byte compiled functions make s equivalent to c.
- **where** print a stack trace of all active function calls.
- **r** invoke a "resume" restart if one is available; interpreted as an R expression otherwise. Typically "resume" restarts are established for continuing from user interrupts.
- **Q** exit the browser and the current evaluation and return to the top-level prompt.

As a small example, using the browser function on **extractETCdata** function is depicted in the snap shot in figure 6. Especially note the output of the browser function in the white patch in the above figure. What we find is that at each punch of the "return" or "enter" button on the computer, a following line appears (an instance shown here were the execution of the browser had reached in the code in **extractETCdata.R**)-

```

> source("extractETCdata.R")
> extractETCdata(1)
Called from: extractETCdata(1)
Browser[1]>
debug at extractETCdata.R#3: if (data.type == 1){
  filename <- "../data/onc2015280x2-A.txt"
} else {

```

```

    filename <- "../data/onc2015280x2-B.txt"
  }
Browser [2]>
.
.

```

What is happening is that we inserted a browser function in `extractETCdata.R` just after `extractETCdata <- function(data.type){`. After compiling `extractETCdata.R` using the `source` function and executing `extractETCdata(1)` at the R prompt `>`, the `browser` function comes into affect. This is shown with an additional `Browser[]>`. Evidence of this is provided by the line stating the following - "Called from: `extractETCdata(1)`". next, on pressing "return", the execution moves to the next command that it needs to execute. This is denoted by debug function and the line reads as "debug at `extractETCdata.R#3:`", meaning that the execution is waiting at command 3 in the code. Along with it, whole command that needs to be executed in one go is also presented. Here it is the `if(data.type == 1) {...} else {...}` command. Since the `data.type == 1` is true, the command `filename <- ../data/onc2015280x2-A.txt` is executed. This is shown in the next line that the browser has to execute, when the above condition holds true. See figure 6.

6.1. Exercise

Please use `browser` function to inspect the values in the variables and see how the code executes for `extractETCdata.R` and `manuscript-2-2.R`.

Results from the search engine can be found in the recently unpublished preprint in Sinha (2023).

7. MYC-HOXB8-EZH2

EZH2 encodes enhancer of zeste homolog 2 and is involved in transcriptional repression via epigenetic modifications. It has been found to be either mutated or over-expressed in many forms of cancer. Over expression of EZH2 leads to silencing of various tumor suppressor genes and thus implicating it for potential roles in tumorigenesis Simon and Lange (2008). EZH2 is a subunit of the highly conserved Polycomb repressive complex 2 (PRC2) which executes the methylation of the histone H3 at lysine-27 O'Meara and Simon (2012). Thus targeting EZH2 has become a major research domain for cancer therapeutics Kim and Roberts (2016). In colon cancer, it has been shown that depletion of EZH2 has led to blocking of proliferation of the cancer Fussbroich et al. (2011). This indicates the fact that tumor suppressor genes get activated and lead to subsequent blocking of the cancer. Also, EZH2 is recruited by PAF to bind with β -catenin transcriptional complex for further Wnt target gene activation, independent of the EZH2 epigenetic modification activities Jung et al. (2013).

Consistent with these, ETC-15922159 treatment lead to down regulation of EZH2 in colorectal cancer samples Madan et al. (2016). This would have activated a lot of tumor suppressor genes that led to subsequent suppression of regrowth in treated cancer samples. More importantly, MYC directly upregulates core components of PRC2,

EZH2 being one of them, in embryonic stem cells Neri et al. (2012). Neri et al. (2012) show that silencing of c-MYC and N-MYC Dardenne et al. (2016) lead to reduction in the expression of PRC2 and thus EZH2. Furthermore, in colorectal cancer cases, Satoh et al. (2017) show that knockdown of MYC led to decrease in EZH2 levels. Similar findings have been observed in Yamaguchi and Hung (2014), Chen et al. (2016) & Fluge et al. (2009). Our in silico findings show consistent results with respect to this down regulation after assigning a low rank of 54 along with MYC-HOXB8.

More specifically, our in silico pipeline is able to approximate the value of the 3rd order combination of MYC-HOXB8-EZH2 by assigning a rank that is consistent with wet lab findings of dual combinatorial behaviour of MYC-EZH2 and MYC-HOXB8. However, since the mechanism of combination of MYC-HOXB8 is not known hitherto, it would be interesting to confirm the behaviour of MYC-HOXB8-EZH2 at 3rd order to reveal a portion of the Wnt pathway's modus operandi in colorectal cancer. Further wet lab tests on these in silico findings will confirm the efficacy of the search engine.

8. Availability and requirements

- Project name - R Code for Machine learning search engine : Ranks/reveals combination of genes/proteins using ETC-1922159 treated CRC static data
- Project (Code) on CERN based Zenodo home page - <https://zenodo.org/records/14636112>
- Project (Preprints) on Open Science Framework home page - <https://osf.io/ngef9/wiki/home/>
- Operating system(s) - Platform independent
- Programming language - R statistical language R Development Core Team (2008)
- Other requirements - (1) *SVM^{Rank}* from https://www.cs.cornell.edu/people/tj/svm_light/svm_rank.html and (2) Sensitivity package in R from <https://cran.r-project.org/web/packages/sensitivity/index.html>
- License - Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International

9. Declarations

- Funding - No institute/university/NGO/company (private/public)/government organization was involved. The project was carried out on personal funds.
- Conflict of interest/Competing interests - There are no conflicts/competing interests to declare.
- Ethics approval and consent to participate - Not applicable.
- Consent for publication - Not applicable.

- Data availability - Data used in this research work has been released online publicly, in a publication in Madan et al. (2016). This data was made available in the form of supplementary table. Related to this data, on NCBI Gene Expression Omnibus (GEO) Series GSE69687 <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/geo/query/acc.cgi?acc=GSE69687>, click on **Download RNA-seq counts** button, it opens a page that contains **Human gene annotation table** (at the bottom of the page). The file **Human.GRCh38.p13.annot.tsv.gz** contains the range of genes with ENSEMBLGENEID all starting with ENSG. This ENSG identifier is used to index the recording of the regulated genes, in the data made available in the supplementary table in Madan et al. (2016). The data itself is available as supplementary material in the journal, however, the indexing of the genes used in the supplementary material is available on NCBI NIH database.
- Author contribution - (1) Concept, design, in silico implementation. (2) Analysis and interpretation of results. (3) Manuscript writing/revision/approval.
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